

THE RVD-1L1 FORM — THE “RITUAL OF SUFFERING” AT THE FIRST CONTACT

First, I want to say that my conclusion from the formative activity is: “**lack of a multidisciplinary team.**” Even after reaching this conclusion, I asked myself why a multidisciplinary team still does not exist in the field, which leads me to a not very academic thought: “**the Portuguese State must be joking!**”

Returning to the RVD:

The victim appears in a place that is **symbolically constraining**, as it represents **Authority**, which is immediately intimidating.

She goes there with a duality: as the offended party she feels **shame**, but also **guilt** for making a complaint against someone she loves. Even so, in desperation, she goes with the hope of “**salvation**,” because she believes that there will be justice.

The victim arrives, begins to speak and, after five minutes, she is handed the **RVD**, which at the end tells the person filling it out: “**based on your experience,**” **are we facing moderate or high risk?** Here enters what **Rosa Saavedra argues**: these PSP officers become **indirect victims**, because they experience the accounts firsthand and many end up advising victims to “**better elaborate their story.**” If we pay attention, we can even understand the feelings they have regarding the **Public Prosecutor’s Office (MP)** about this.

If the victim speaks with a **psychologist who is not a forensic psychologist**, two things happen:

That empathetic look of suffering, in which the victim even becomes worried about whether the psychologist might be suffering because of the account being given.

Then there is the one who listens and starts asking questions that **lead nowhere.**

Then come the **judges**, who want **evidence**, the best being **scars and bruises**. The **emotional and economic dimension**, which this course unit taught me about, is **not even taken into account**. If it were not for this course unit, I would not even know the article existed.

In the **first question of the RVD**, it asks how many years ago the first episode of **physical violence** occurred. How would the victim know the date? How would the

victim distinguish a **push**, a **slap**, from an **act of beating**? Because if she knew how to distinguish these things, she would possibly **not be a victim of domestic violence**.

The **second question** asks whether the aggressor used physical violence against other members of the household and domestic animals. If the victim lives only with the aggressor, there will be no others, and much less witnesses. Regarding domestic animals, he may not beat them, but he may feed the animals food that will harm them in order to place the victim in panic, and then the aggressor becomes the helper, who even takes the animal to the hospital.

Question four is well formulated, but something is missing:

“Does the offender deprive you of sex as a form of punishment, telling you that he will only do it when you deserve it?”

Question five is the TRUTH.

Question five is the basis of all this and of how everything is structured to...

5. Was medical attention required after any aggression and/or did the injuries compromise the normal daily activities of the victim or another family member?

The victim looks and thinks: *I am not blind nor crippled, my body is functional*, and answers **NO**.

What the system wants to hear has been concluded.

And where is the **psychological injury**? Perhaps these victims are unemployed, unable to work due to trauma and post-traumatic stress, and their past may be filled with professional successes and achievements, where they were possibly a reference for many people, and now they cannot even leave the house or relate to others.

The **sixth question** asks whether the violence has been increasing. Well then, for **73 years the 12-step groups have been saying this about drugs**: *“one is too many and a thousand are never enough.”* After 73 years of knowing that once is enough, we still ask the victim of domestic violence the sixth question!

The **eighth question** — how would the victim know what he is capable of! When the relationship began, how could she know that one day she would become a victim of domestic violence, let alone whether he would be capable of killing her.

The **ninth question** is an attempt to find witnesses so that the victim of domestic violence can then be considered a victim of domestic violence. For me, it is a **manipulative and abusive question!**

The **tenth question**, which should be part of the eighteenth, should include:
“After the end of the relationship, are you pursued by SMS or in person by the aggressor? Does the aggressor reject the end of the relationship — explain how.”

Here, if the article were validated, they would know that the aggressor **does not leave the victim**, because he needs someone to assault, to use economically and psychologically. The victim may even try, but he does not allow it, and the court does not apply a restraining measure or an electronic bracelet, because **that costs money**.

From the **eleventh to the fourteenth question**, everything is about the aggressor. One even starts to feel sorry for the aggressor — this should never appear here! This should be about the **victim**, not the aggressor, and the victim should never have to think or place herself in the aggressor’s position. Suddenly the victim remembers: *“oh yes, he is addicted, ok, he is sick; oh yes, he had childhood problems; he has psychological problems, poor thing.”*

Here — and I would like to witness this — I imagine the victim’s legs sliding to the right side of the chair, like someone ready to leave that interrogation, feeling so guilty for being there that she only wants to leave and go hug the aggressor.

The nineteenth question: if the victim has special needs??????

No, she is perfectly fine! Ready for **another round of physical, psychological and economic abuse!**

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